

COVID-19 and Gendered Burden in the Context of Structural Inequality

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Abstract

Women are not only victim of structural inequality but also being discriminated due to their status in social hierarchy. The gendered roles assigned to women by society add more social, economic and psychological burden on them during any crisis or disaster situation. In Covid -19 pandemic the social and household responsibilities increased burden and their vulnerabilities. It can be viewed from different social, economic and psychological perspectives. In this context the present paper is an attempt for critically analyzing gender roles in covid-19 pandemic with special focus of institutional response towards women.

Key words: Structural Inequality, Covid-19, Gendered Burden, Burden of Care.

Introduction

India is the world largest democratic country and it is known for its rich social, cultural and regional diversity. But if we critically analyze the phenomenon, this diversity also accompanied by various forms of structural inequalities. The benefit of the nation's development and growth is not reaching out to all the people equally. There are sections of society who are marginalized and deprived of equal opportunities in comparison to other dominant groups of Indian society. They are not only victim of structural inequality but also being discriminated due to their status in social hierarchy. These groups are women, scheduled castes (SCs), scheduled tribes (STs), Persons with disability (PWDs), minority and economically poor sections of society etc. Among all, the important and most vulnerable section is women. The intersectionality of different parameters of development and well being suggested that women from gendered lens are more deprived and less likely to progress in comparison to men. They are not only in need of special attention and focus of the government but also entitled to get their due share of growth and development of the country. However, the Constitution of India binds all citizen in common thread with security of fundamental rights and it is guiding the states to follow directive principles of state policy to deliver services in best interest of its citizens with inclusive approach. During Covid-19 the world was stuck with limited option, restricted physical mobility, closed business, work, institutions and networks, heavy burden of Covid-19 infections, people and community immobility and helplessness. The governments came up with immediate suitable plan and strategies, but still people were overburdened with their social, economic and psychological issues. In this context the gendered discussion not only important from providing immediate assistance to women, but at the larger level it is equally important from policy perspectives. Let us look at some important areas of discussion and intervention. The following section of the paper is dealing with the women issue especially in the context of Covid-19 pandemic.

COVID-19 and Gendered Burden

Under the constitutional framework, all the citizens are equally entitled to get protection from government to maintain the state of well being. Constitution also makes state duty bound to towards protecting social and economic interests of the people through various policy, strategies and interventions. Also special attention to be given to marginalized and excluded sections of the society with exclusive provisions. In this direction various efforts were made by government to provide immediate support and rescue to the women. "The Government welfare schemes and self-help groups (SHGs) were important in helping survey respondents navigate the pandemic. About one in three women considered the government's support crucial in weathering the crisis, on par with perceived support from family. This is likely because of the multiple schemes the government built on

Special Issue on 'Covid-19 Pandemic and Well Being : Perspectives on Social Aspects' and leveraged during the pandemic. For example, it launched an INR 1.7 lakh crore relief package under the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Yojana (PMGKY) scheme to bolster existing welfare schemes. The relief package supported cash transfer into Jan Dhan accounts, increased the MGNREGA wage payment, and doubled collateral-free loans for SHGs (The Wire 2020).

During the Covid-19 the Government of India has taken many initiatives through government policy and programmes to maintain healthy and stable society. But it cannot be possible unless government would give equal and fair attention to create inclusive society by focusing on marginalized sections of society especially in area of social and gender equality, education, health, and sustained livelihood.

The gendered dimension of global health crisis was already in discussion by UN. Since Ebola and Zika (2016) it is acknowledged that health crisis have differential impact in the society, especially on women in children from gendered perspectives. The Covid-19 and its impact on people is beyond what we see in general due self isolation and physical distancing policy. In gendered context it added burden on women for domestic work, children and elderly care. It becomes sole responsibility of women to manage work and home simultaneously.

The Covid 19 exposed women for enhanced working hour i.e. unpaid workload. It not only increases their working hours at home for enhanced care roles but also chances of loosing on jobs due to contractual nature of jobs and restrictions on businesses/work due to covid-19. Their own health issues are getting neglected due to limited access to health care services and lack of attention. "COVID-19 is expected to push an estimated 47 million additional women and girls into extreme poverty and further widen the gender poverty gap. Women have done 29% more childcare per week than men during the pandemic, based on data from 16 countries. Nearly 1 in 2 women reported that they or someone they know have experienced violence since the start of the pandemic, according to survey results from 13 countries"(UN Women).

Violence against women increased globally and received attention of different stakeholders. WHO and UN issued various guidelines to create support online support systems and assistance for reporting. The child marriage and chances of physical and emotional violence are expected to increase during Covid-19. The cases of mental health crisis are being reported at various platforms globally. In India women under patriarchal systems are more vulnerable to all above problems. At the same time their health rights are also getting violated due to lack of knowledge, awareness and absence of support systems.

*Gender-based violence, already a global crisis before the pandemic, has intensified since the outbreak of COVID-19. Lockdowns and other mobility restrictions have left many women trapped with their abusers, isolated from social contact and support networks. Increased economic precarity has further limited many women's ability to leave abusive situations. COVID-driven economic and social instability will also heighten the risk of child marriage, female genital mutilation and human trafficking. At the same time, the pandemic has exposed women leaders to backlash, leading to threats, abuse and harassment both online and offline. Violence against women leaders can prevent them from carrying out their duties regardless of the position they hold (UN Women 2021). In this context the government and other stakeholders of global society are advised to take steps to protect rights of women and to come forward for preventive strategies for providing help and assistance in the time of crisis. In India various steps were taken to deal with the issue, 24*7 online helpline number, formation of SHGs(World Bank 2020) at local level, government advisories are some important measures to acknowledge. At the same time government also provided relief to people through mass level Covid-19 protection kits distribution, ration allocation and Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalayan Yojna (PMGKY) fund transfer etc.*

Work from home and domestic care burden

The reports from media suggest that working from home added more burden on the working professionals. It is due to multiple responsibilities at domestic front on women, that makes them more vulnerable in the situation of Covid-19. The report by Sanganai (2020), highlights that lack of digital infrastructural support made working professionals more frustrated and helpless in the situation of imposed lockdown and work from home policy. Around 80 % felt frustrated due to network issues, 42% faced internet connection issues, and 75% internet distraction issues. There was no flexibility of work hours as majorly the online work was scheduled as it was in offline. This not only added problems related to internet connection, arranging work place at home, which was having clashes with daily routine of other family members(The Economic Times 2020).

Women around the world spend more time in care work in both professional and personal life. The burden of care is primarily on women. It increased drastically during covid-19 , that also accompanied with various crucial factors, such as increased burden of care without any assistance, more chances of abuse and violence, lack of

health care support and proper diet. This increased unpaid care burden is not accounted in any form and acknowledged by any institution because women are generally expected to do the household chores within patriarchal norms and from gendered assigned roles norms of the society. The discussion on unpaid work and burden of work on women revealed that, “ *Women’s unpaid responsibilities at home and other forms of unpaid work such as cattle rearing or farm labour are recognised as some of the biggest barriers preventing them from getting into, remaining in, and progressing in the labour force. One of the documented effects of unpaid work is having less time to perform paid work—women spend disproportionately more time than men doing unpaid care work, making it difficult for them to work otherwise (The Wire 2020).* Further reports suggest that, “ *In India, for example, men devote 36 minutes to unpaid care responsibilities, out of which 36% goes into housework, with the remaining time spent on shopping, care for household members, and travel related to household activities. Out of the six hours women devote to unpaid care activities, the portion of time specifically spent on housework reaches 85% (OECD, Development Centre 2014)*

Impact of Covid-19 on labour and work

The issue of labour and work is not only related to employment but having direct linkages with food security, decent living, housing, health, education and so on. As per estimates, “*The employment crisis became an unfortunate consequence, as India cycled through lockdowns of varying severity and duration during the COVID-19 pandemic. The unemployment rate, at approximately 7.2% in January 2020, shot up to 23.5% in April 2020, and fluctuated over the year to end at about 7% (up from approximately 5.3% in 2019). Based on these numbers, it would seem that employment has recovered to some extent. However, a closer look at the situation reveals a clear gender bias in this recovery, especially for women from low-income households*” (The Wire 2020). Also if we look at closely the issues of labour majority of population is working in informal and unorganized sector, this sector is far from any direct social security protection. In Covid -19, we have witnessed the plights of migrated workers; it was not only shocking but also emotionally heavy moment for all Indians. The miles they have walked without any protection raised very pertinent question are government efforts sufficient to protect the decent living for millions of people, those are contributing day and night for country development and growth.

In context of work from home, another important aspect is related to lack of clarity about working place during Covid -19. The “*Occupational Safety, Health and Working Conditions Code, 2020 (OSH Code): OSH Code defines “Establishment” as a place employing workers, connoting a physical space where work takes place. Any other place is not an establishment; hence questions of occupational safety and health of workers working outside a physical establishment arise. The definition of “Establishment” is also not as inclusive as that of “workplace” under Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013 (POSH Act), which includes even transportation used for work, as workplace. Though different in its aims, the POSH Act establishes workplace as a fluid concept. With WFH becoming the new normal, the concept of “Establishment” may need broadening, to sufficiently accommodate occupational safety and health of workers working from home*”(TOI, 2022). In view of above discussion the WFH concept seems to be speeded without any discussion on short and long term implications on women. The women those are already under double burden of unpaid care work, official work responsibility and management of Covid-19 are exposed to unprotected environment with regard to safety and security, that need to be provided by employer.

Reproductive Health and Nutrition

World health Organisation (WHO) defines health that, Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. The enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being without distinction of race, religion, political belief, economic or social condition”. Further the health is also explained through many factors combine together to affect the health of individuals and communities. Whether people are healthy or not, is determined by their circumstances and environment. To a large extent, factors such as where we live, the state of our environment, genetics, our income and education level, and our relationships with friends and family all have considerable impacts on health, whereas the more commonly considered factors such as access and use of health care services often have less of an impact (WHO, 2017).

In the above view women health is not only important from her own development view point but also from child growth and development. A woman during pregnancy and post pregnancy is required special attention and support from immediate and family and external institutions. The “UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2.2

indicates towards “ending all forms of malnutrition by 2030 for children under 5”. The number of undernourished people increased 720 to 811 million people in world faced hunger in 2020(GHI, 2021)”.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) came into effect in January 2016, and they will continue to guide United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) policy and funding until 2030. India is signatory to it and is committed to global society agenda to reduce all forms of Inequality. The Sustainable Development Goals are focusing on global efforts to end poverty, to end discrimination and to ensure peace and well being of all. All SDGs are based on certain themes such as people, planet, prosperity, peace and partnership. These themes have given broader view to include all possible matters of human welfare and well being. The intention is to create equal spaces and opportunities for all, protection of interest of all sections of the society, sensitive growth and development and to build peaceful global society. In context of inclusion the Goal 10 of Sustainable Development is "to reduce inequality within and among countries". The Goal 16 of the UN Sustainable Development is dedicated to the promotion of peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, the provision of access to justice for all, and building effective, accountable institutions at all levels.

Nutrition is a critical part of health and development. Better nutrition is related to improved infant, child and maternal health, stronger immune systems, safer pregnancy and childbirth, lower risk of non-communicable diseases (such as diabetes and cardiovascular disease), and longevity. Healthy children learn better. People with adequate nutrition are more productive and can create opportunities to gradually break the cycles of poverty and hunger. Malnutrition, in every form, presents significant threats to human health. Today the world faces a double burden of malnutrition that includes both under nutrition and overweight, especially in low- and middle-income countries. There are multiple forms of malnutrition, including under nutrition (wasting or stunting), inadequate vitamins or minerals, overweight, obesity, and resulting diet-related non communicable diseases. The developmental, economic, social, and medical impacts of the global burden of malnutrition are serious and lasting for individuals and their families, for communities and for countries.(WHO 2021). The women health and nutrition is correlated from both women and child development view point. It is also directly linked to burden on women of unpaid workload and lack of social security and safety nets for women at work places. It adds more multiple burden on women and impacting her health negatively, the need to pay attention to her hardship (The wire 2021).

The way after Covid-19

The exposure of Covid-19 pandemic highlighted important questions, as a global society, are we ready with future planning from gendered perspectives. The assessment of social policy and programmes need to be planned in accordance to gender and structural inequality and social, cultural, economic, and political remedies to be prepared with short and long term intervention to overcome from these gendered inequalities. The overall well-being of the women is possible through giving attention to her unpaid care giving work, labour and working conditions, proper infrastructural and policy arrangements. The need is to connect with supportive agencies for implementation of timely policy matters. The use of technology and media is crucial in attaining the balance and equal spaces. The women agency/groups should be supported by legal institutions for their safety and protection within personal and public spaces.

Many arrangements have been done by many countries including India during the time of lockdown in Covid-19, in absence of any concrete research we don't know how in the long run Covid-19 is going to impact countries, therefore these arrangements need to be continued even after the covid-19 and most importantly forever to create more empowering state of women for their overall well being.

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